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DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF AN E-LEARNING TOOL FOR TECHNICAL MECHANICS TO PROMOTE TRANSFER KNOWLEDGE OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The individual support of students in basic subjects such as technical mechanics (TM) is difficult to implement due to large and heterogeneous groups. Students tend to memorization due to the conventional teaching concept, they cannot transfer the theoretical content to unknown contexts. According to Müller-Slany (2018) every mechanical exercise, regardless of its complexity, is subject to the same solution methodology. It implies solving the exercises with a model. Reflection and transfer, the last step in the modelling cycle, are often not considered in the teaching [1]. Training the structure of mechanical exercises is a basic skill required for the last step of the modelling cycle and is therefore essential and principal for teaching.

The aim of this project is to support transfer knowledge by development and implementation of an e-learning tool that supports the individual learning process of every student by giving faults-related feedback in the form of prompts. Prompts increase problem-solving skills [2]. Furthermore, they help with the self-regulated solution process and support metacognitive reflection [3]. Faults can then be identified with the help of this extensive faults- prompts - system. By solving contextualized pre-structured exercises with differences in depth of structure the development of transfer knowledge [4] should be increased. As part of a formative qualitative evaluation, suitable prompts are developed and then the influence of the exercise format is examined in an experimental design.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Individual support for students in bachelor's basic subjects, such as technical mechanics (TM), is difficult to implement due to large and heterogeneous groups. The students have heterogeneous levels of performance, because i.a. the previous knowledge in the technical subjects varies significantly at the start of the first two semesters. Students tend to memorize, they cannot transfer the theoretical content to unknown contexts, even though they initially have a positive self-efficacy that represents a discrepancy with the actual performance.

This can be a reason for the high dropout rates of students of engineering bachelor's courses, especially in the first two semesters. Another reason can be the lack of entry qualifications in mathematics and physics. The TM requires mathematical modeling of professional interconnections in order to be able to analyze mechanical systems. A detailed competence modelling of students in the TM in engineering courses has already been carried out (cf. [5]). Results of this study show that mathematical skills of the students have a strong influence on the performance in statics.

Students hardly reflect on the learning process and modeling skills are not dominant either ([7]).

One aspect of achieving a better metacognition is to foster self regulated learning. The other way to promote metacognition, this time in a direct way, is the use of strategy training in form of scaffolding. For this approach contextualized prestructured tasks with varies depth of structure are integrated in the system. The task format at the beginning is structured very strong with many subtasks and after solving the tasks this way successfully, the students achieve more open taskformats. This scaffolding element is named fading ([9], [6]).

Metacognition is the knowledge about the own learning process, so planning, monitoring and reflection about the learning behaviour should be supported with these approaches. By reflection the own learning process students can train their modeling skills through seeing the strategy they used by solving the task.

According to Dammann [5], the basic selection of TM exercises at each university is the same, the task types are similarly structured. In statics, the following topics are always relevant in teaching: resulting force and moments, support reactions, trusses, internal forces and centre of gravity.

According to Müller-Slany [1], every mechanical exercise regardless of its complexity is subject to the same solution methodology. This describes solving the exercises as modelling. Figure 1 shows this schematic structure of a mechanical exercise based on the modeling cycle according to Müller-Slany.

Figure 1: Structure of mechanical tasks (cf. [1])

The practice of this modelling showed in Figure 1, i.e. the schematic solving of tasks, takes a lot of time in teaching. Exam results show that this model identification and modelling itself is often not implemented in teaching.

The learning outcomes within the framework of the TM are often only oriented towards the pattern-recognition and repetition. Reflection and transfer, the last step in the modeling cycle, are therefore often not reflected in teaching [1]. Training the structure of mechanical tasks, i.e. modeling, is a basic skill required for the last stage of the modeling cycle and is therefore essential and principal for teaching.

There are currently only a few eLearning tools in the TM, and none of the existing offers include one that specifically supports this pattern-recognition and then independent modeling. A comprehensive market analysis in 2018 shows that there is no e-learning tool that requires an individual, interactive approach, specifically discloses and trains the scheme of mechanical tasks or helps with the independent fault analysis. The existing tools use formats such as multiple choice or the entry of a final solution such as Lon Capa or usable for reviewing, the drawing of systems to get a result with automatic calculation of the demanded dimensions such as RatzFatz at the University of Wuppertal.

2 METHODOLOGY

With the eLearning Tool developed in this project, it should be possible to support the individual learning process of the students better by promoting the modeling in solving mechanical tasks and focusing on the independent fault analysis.

With regard to these aims, the focus is on the one hand on showing the schema, i.e. the model, and on the other hand on the transfer of this schema to unknown contexts for better problem solving skills.

2.1 STUDY APPROACH

The exercise concept to be developed based on two main aspects: on the one hand there should be integrated scaffolded tasks to show and train the scheme of the exercise by dissolving the given task structure through many guided subtasks in the course of processing and on the other hand a feedback-system with fault-related prompts should be implemented. The influence of both interventions (scaffolded tasks and feedback-system) on the modelling, i.e. pattern-recognition and transfer, should be examined in this study approach.

Hence, the following research questions are to be investigated:

1. What influence does the scaffolding have on the modeling?
2. What influence does the feedback system have on the modeling?

2.2 METHOD AND DESIGN

The effects of the two mentioned interventions have to be examined individually, so in this study a 2x2 design is chosen. Figure 2 shows the test composition.

		Scaffolded Tasks	
		yes	no
Feedback-System	yes	Group 1	Group 2
	no	Group 3	Group 4

Figure 2: 2x2 Design

For the examination the mechanical engineering students are divided into four different groups to depict all combinations of intervention. Every group consists of ca. 30 students. The implemented exercises contain of the regular exercises which are used in lecture and exams and also of new created ones that fit to the design (contextualized tasks, similar tasks which varies in structure, context, values, etc.) and they will be adapted to prestrucuted (sub-)tasks and fault-related prompts depending on the fault type. These exercises are then made available online in the eLearning Tool. So the processing, data collection and data evaluation takes place online.

The blended learning concept contains of regular teaching and the eLearning Tool, which specifically supports the teaching on-site. A lecture will take place on-site. The exercises, which are provided via the eLearning Tool, serve as a prerequisite for the exam, so that the processing of the tasks in the eLearning Tool is ensured. All

students have to submit the exercises online in the form of an exercise sheet. There is also a supplementary teaching exercise on-site, in which these tasks are dealt with and questions regarding to the eLearning Tool can be asked, increasing tasks are worked on and also the time in teaching can be scheduled for reflection on the tasks and results. There is also a tutorial for the students, in which they can clarify specific questions and problems with a student as a tutor at the same level.

For an independent fault analysis, to optimize performance by disclosing your own weaknesses such as basic mathematical problems, an extensive fault-prompt-system with fault-specific prompts of different levels of help is integrated. This structure enables individual detection of weaknesses for rapid performance improvement. Furthermore the heterogeneous levels of performance of the students are taken into account, because each student decides for himself which help he needs in what level of detail. The fault-related prompts helps the students with the solution process. Prompts support the students' metacognitive reflection by giving prompts themselves [3]. Studies also show that prompts train better problem-solving skills [2]. One aspect of better metacognition is to make sure a selfregulated learning. This could be achieved through the use of (the level of) prompts, videos and the number of tasks in the exercise sheets which depends on the solution quote in the individual tasks in each level of complexity. It's necessary to make sure that all students use the prompts because only then a better metacognition can be achieved ([7]).

Through parameterized tasks in the eLearning Tool, each student receives his / her own tasks, which requires independent discussion of these. Each task is structured as a learning task, it is divided into many, small sub-tasks. The students have to solve the subtasks themselves in order to stimulate the learning activity. The next subtask will not be released until the subtask has been solved successfully. The reflection, which is only considered after the solution has been worked out (cf. Figure 1), is initially neglected because solutions of (sub-) tasks is not specified in the tool.

The small-scale, scaffolded task format should support the pattern-recognition of the mechanical tasks. In the further course of processing, more open task formats can be activated, i.e. non-pre-structured tasks with significantly fewer to no subtasks. By cancellation of this small-scale system and introducing tasks with new, unknown contexts, the intention is to promote the transfer knowledge of the students [4].

All tasks of the exercise sheets are presented as 'learning cards'. The students of the group with scaffolding units get different taskformats of different levels of complexity. With increase of complexity the number of full-prestructured tasks reduces. The task solving quote (and the use of supporting videos) regulates the number of tasks to be solved. There are three task formats integrated in the system: the closed one is the one with the most subtasks, the semi-open format is with a given free body diagram so the calculation of a target variable have to be done by

the students themselves (find the right equilibrium conditions fitting to the given free body diagram and then calculate the unknown variable). The last format is the open one, in which the students have to calculate on their own (not in the system presented) and just need to give the endsolution. For the test students have to load up their solution with a detailed solution process in moodle so that the details of schema recognition can be analyzed.

Following test instruments are developed to check the effectiveness of the intervention: Expertise test in a pre-post- format to measure the increase in knowledge and a questionnaire that contains tasks for investigation for schema recognition.

2.3 MECHWEB – REPRESENTATION OF AN EXAMPLE TASK

This concept paper includes an eLearning Tool, which is structured as followed regarding to the mentioned aims and the modelling cycle showed in Figure 1: The free body diagram of a model should be able to be implemented interactively in the system. For this purpose, node points are first drawn in the given illustration of a machine or system, at which forces or moments, external or internal exposures engage. Then forces and moments are drawn in at these node points, angles, e.g. for the calculation of components (for later trigonometric calculations), labels of forces and moments for assignment to the equilibrium conditions inserted and forces with a dependent direction drawn in. Then the three equilibrium conditions are set up, these are all dependent on the drawn free body diagram (direction specification, direction of rotation, labeling, etc.). After this subtask, the equations are transformed to unknown variables and resolved step by step, and values for the variables are given with unit and sign - depending on the free body diagram. The fault-prompt-system that can be reached via the surface mask.

When working on the individual subtasks, prompts are displayed in form of an information box, which is activated by clicking the "Hints"- button in the upper, outer menu system. This outer menu also enables the current status to be saved for flexible processing, calling up new, similar tasks and especially checking the results after each sub-task has been carried out. If the result is correct, the feedback is "correctly", the result entry is colored green and the next subtask is activated. If the result is incorrect, the feedback is "wrong" and a specific fault is noted. For faults such as forgotten unit, wrong value, too many or too few forces plotted, unknown variable, trigonometric problems, converting problems etc. individual feedback through prompts is given depending on the fault. For this purpose, the information box with the prompts is called up and the subtask is executed again.

If no advice helps, after five failed attempts, i.e. five times the "wrong result" indication after passing through the prompts, the task is stopped with the note: Please look for help. This help can be requested online in the forum, obtained on site in the learning center at the HelpDesk or requested in the courses, especially the exercises and tutorials.

To focus on a self regulated learning all tasks have to be solved by the students themselves and they don't get the solution. So they are forced to solve the problem and think about a possible way solving the problem. When doing a failure they can choose whether they need help in form of prompts (indirect supporting of metacognition) and in what detail they need this help (level of prompts) or they can look a video that shows a similar task solution based on the same solution methodology. The integrated prompts are questions to recognize the position in the modelling cycle and reflect on the problem solving process. This prompts could be reason-justification prompts or rule-based prompts ([8]) to support transfer knowledge and strategy knowledge (modeling skills). Prompts could be e.g.: What do you need for the calculation of the force?, For what intend have you done the free body diagram? What can you do with the marked forces in the free body diagram? What are relevant variables for calculation a value for variable X? What is the next step to find out the value of X?, In what relation are the marked forces in the free body diagram with your unknown variable?

3 RESULTS

3.1 PRELIMINARY STUDIES

In the winter semester 18/19 there was a qualitative, videographed study in the form of thinking aloud with five students. Results have shown that the heavily scaffolded (sub-)tasks enable the specific detection of problems. The differentiation between faults based on mechanical problems and the ones based on mathematical problems could be identified clearly. So the students could be guided through help options specifically. Also the schema disclosed by the task format was partially adapted directly in the course of the further processing of the exercise sheet.

The more exercises the students have completed, the more the modeling skills were better performed and the schema was recognized and adapted to the following exercises. 80% of the probands calculated with all steps from the modeling cycle and solve the problems in sequence with less help (less hints were needed to achieve the right solution). By opening the task, i.e. reducing the taskstructure, they transferred their modeling knowledge and were better prepared to solve the problems and they know what problems they have and how to solve them.

A paper-pencil test in the winter semester 19/20 with 26 students has taken place. The test was structured in four scaffolded exercises and two open formed exercises. The schema which has to be used by solving the problem was the same in all exercises. The difficulty level increases step by step. Results showed that in some cases the structure of the scaffolded tasks was automatically applied to the open-format tasks while working on exercises with the same difficulty level. The more complex the exercise got, the more difficult was it for the students to see the schema and transfer it to the open formed tasks.

4 SUMMARY

To support the problem solving skills of the students in technical mechanics regarding to modelling an eLearning tool with scaffolded tasks and a specific feedback system will be used. With this composition it should be possible to recognize the modelling of a mechanical task and transfer it to open-format tasks and tasks of other context. Furthermore the individual learning process is focused by parameterized tasks and individual prompts.

The tasks and test instruments are currently being developed. For the selection and construction of the tasks, actually used tasks will be classified into different categories (difficulty levels, type of context, etc.) in order to be able to control the difficulty of the tasks. Therefore difficulty levels are operationalized with the help of complexity levels to be defined.

The pilot study will be carried out in a mechanical engineering course in the winter semester 20/21. The main study will take place a year later.

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